

Some New 2-Arylimino-3-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones and 3-Aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidiones

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Nine new 3-aryl-2-arylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones have been prepared and twelve new 3-aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidiones have been synthesised. The products of their decomposition and hydrolysis have been identified.

In view of the significant biological properties of thiazolidones and thiazolidiones as inhibitors of electrically induced and metrazole induced convulsions, local anaesthetics, bactericides, and fungicides, preparations of some new 2-arylimino-3-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones (I) and 3-aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidiones (II) were taken up for biological studies (Bhargava *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 2353; this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 49; 1956, **33**, 596; 1957, **34**, 475, 776). Thiazolidones have been obtained by the interaction of *sym*-diaryl thioureas prepared from aniline, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-toluidine, *m*-chloroaniline, *o*- and *p*-phenetidine, *o*-anisidine, and β -naphthylamine with α -chloropropionic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and absolute ethanol under conditions laid down by Bhargava *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) according to the reaction :

The structure of the compound has been corroborated by its degradation products and characteristic derivatives obtained. 3-Phenyl-2-phenylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidone decomposes to *sym*-diphenylurea and methylthioglycollic acid when refluxed with a strong solution of ethanolic KOH and to 3-phenyl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidione when hydrolysed with HCl (conc.).

Similarly 3-aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidiones have been obtained by the reaction of *sym*-diaryl thiourea of aniline, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-toluidine, *m*- and *p*-chloroaniline, *o*- and *p*-phenetidine, *o*- and *p*-anisidine, and α - and β -naphthylamines with α -chloropropionic acid in a mixture of glacial acetic acid and hydrochloric acid. 3-Phenyl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidione on decomposition with KOH has yielded aniline.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Phenyl-2-phenylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidone.—A mixture of diphenylthiourea (10 g.), α -chloropropionic acid (8 c.c.), fused sodium acetate (7 g.), and ethanol (50 c.c.) was refluxed on a water bath for 5 hours. After distilling ethanol, the substance was washed with water, when a gummy product was obtained. It solidified on keeping overnight in contact with water. It was crystallised from ethanol in a colorless form, m.p. 105°. (Found : S, 11.10. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2S$ requires S, 11.34%).

Similarly other 3-aryl-2-arylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones were prepared from different thioureas, as recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

3-Aryl-2-arylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidones.

Thioureas.	Reflux time.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
<i>sym.</i> -Diphenyl-	5 hrs.	Colorless	105°	$C_{16}H_{14}ON_2S$	11.10	11.34
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	6	Do	110°	$C_{18}H_{16}ON_2S$	10.7	10.32
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	6	Yellow	98°	$C_{18}H_{16}ON_2S$	10.78	10.32
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	8	Colorless	160°	$C_{18}H_{16}ON_2S$	10.35	10.32
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-	6	Do	122°	$C_{16}H_{12}ON_2Cl_2S$	9.5	9.11
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>o</i> -anisyl-	6	Do	150°	$C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_2S$	9.58	9.35
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>o</i> -phenetyl-	6	Do	130°	$C_{20}H_{22}O_2N_2S$	8.90	8.64
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -phenetyl-	6	Brown	108°	$C_{20}H_{22}O_2N_2S$	8.24	8.64
<i>sym.</i> -Di- β -naphthyl-	18	Do	184°	$C_{24}H_{18}ON_2S$	8.41	8.37

Decomposition of 3-Phenyl-2-phenylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidone with KOH.—A mixture of 3-phenyl-2-phenylimino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidone (2 g.), *N*-ethanolic KOH (20 c.c.), and ethanol (15 c.c.) was refluxed for 3 hours; the contents were poured into water and filtered. After washing free of alkali, the residue was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 238-39°. The mixed m.p. with a pure specimen of *sym.*-diphenylurea remained undepressed.

The filtrate developed a greenish blue colour with sodium nitroprusside, which is characteristic of thioglycollic and alkylthioglycollic acids, thereby confirming the presence of α -methylthioglycollic acid.

Hydrolysis with Ethanolic HCl to 3-Phenyl-5-methyl-2, 4-thiazolidione.—3-Phenyl-2-phenyl-4-imino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidone (2 g.), ethanol (15 c.c.), and HCl (conc., 5 c.c.) were refluxed on a water bath for 6 hours. After distilling ethanol, the mixture was poured into water and filtered. The residue was washed with water, dried, and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 80°. (Found : S, 15.55. $C_{10}H_8O_2NS$ requires S, 15.45%).

3-Phenyl-5-methyl-2, 4-thiazolidione.—A mixture of *sym.*-diphenylthiourea (12 g.), α -chloropropionic acid (12 c.c.), and glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) was refluxed for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water and kept overnight. The solid obtained was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 80°. (Found : S, 15.17. $C_{10}H_8O_2NS$ requires S, 15.45%).

Similarly other 3-aryl-5-methyl-2, 4-thiazolidiones were prepared from different thioureas, as recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

3-Aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidiones.

Thioureas.	Reflux time.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
<i>sym.</i> -Diphenyl-	3	Yellow	80°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ NS	15.17	15.45
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	3	Pink	105°	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	14.49	14.47
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	3	Brown	120°	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	14.3	14.47
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	5	Colorless	140°	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	14.47	14.47
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-	3	Do	120°	C ₂₀ H ₉ O ₂ NCIS	13.61	13.25
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-	5	Do	160°	C ₂₀ H ₉ O ₂ NCIS	12.99	13.25
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>o</i> -anisyl-	3	Brown	125°	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	13.96	13.50
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -anisyl-	3	Do	180°	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	13.62	13.50
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>o</i> -phenetyl-	4	Colorless	130°	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS	12.48	12.75
<i>sym.</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -phenetyl-	3	Do	70°	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS	12.46	12.75
<i>sym.</i> -Di- α -naphthyl-	12	Brown	72°	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	12.51	12.46
<i>sym.</i> -Di- β -naphthyl-	12	Do	69°	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	12.76	12.46

Decomposition of 3-Phenyl-5-methyl-2, 4-thiazolidione.—The thiazolidione (1 g.) was boiled with 40% KOH (50 c.c.) on a water bath for 3 hours. The reaction mixture on distillation gave a liquid which was confirmed as aniline by preparation of its azo- β -naphthol derivative.

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